

Design and Fabrication of Three-Dimensional Scaffolds (Scaffolds) Made of PLA, PCL, and Flexible Polymers Using 3D Printing for Tissue Engineering Applications

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Three-dimensional scaffolds are key structures in tissue engineering (TE), as they mimic the natural extracellular matrix, facilitating cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation during tissue regeneration processes. Proper design in terms of geometry, size, and porosity is essential for developing effective treatments in regenerative medicine (RM). In this context, the present study focused on the construction of a scaffold bank made of polylactic acid (PLA), polycaprolactone (PCL), and flexible polymers (FLEX) through 3D printing using the fused deposition modeling (FDM) technique, intending to promote TE research at the Unidad Central del Valle del Cauca (UCEVA). Scaffolds were designed with two geometries (cubic and cylindrical) and four pore types (square, triangular, rectangular, and diagonal at 45°). Thirty-two scaffolds were fabricated for each biomaterial, totaling 96 units with variations in pore size. The methodology included calibration of the REGEMAT 3D R4L printer, definition of specific printing parameters for each polymer, and evaluation of the scaffolds using inverted optical and stereoscopic microscopy. Results showed that the scaffolds exhibited controlled porosity, adequate structural stability, and favorable morphological characteristics. This scaffold bank is proposed as an experimental and educational resource that will enable the development of future research aimed at tissue regeneration, such as bone, skin, cartilage, and tendons. It also strengthens institutional capabilities in biofabrication, contributing to the establishment of standardized protocols that enhance reproducibility in 3D printing. The bank can be used by students and researchers from various disciplines, positioning UCEVA as a regional benchmark in technologies applied to biomedicine.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18246361

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tissue engineering (TE) has emerged as one of the most promising areas within regenerative medicine (RM) due to its ability to develop therapeutic solutions aimed at repairing, regenerating, or replacing damaged tissues and organs. This discipline combines principles of cell biology, materials science, and biomedical engineering to design three-dimensional structures known as scaffolds that simulate the extracellular matrix, facilitating processes such as cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation [1, 2].

Its application extends to a wide range of pathologies, from musculoskeletal injuries to complex bone defects, focusing on improving patients' quality of life and reducing reliance on traditional invasive treatments [3].

In this context, the fabrication of three-dimensional scaffolds using 3D printing technologies has gained prominence due to its ability to produce structures with precise geometries, controlled porosity, and adjustable mechanical properties.

Among additive manufacturing methods, fused deposition modeling (FDM) stands out for its accessibility, low cost, and compatibility with biomedical polymers such as polylactic acid (PLA), polycaprolactone (PCL), and flexible materials (FLEX). These biopolymers exhibit ideal properties for clinical applications, including biocompatibility, biodegradability, low toxicity, and ease of thermal processing [4–6].

However, efficient use of these technologies in academic and institutional settings requires detailed knowledge of printing conditions. Factors such as extrusion temperature, deposition speed, pore geometry, layer thickness, and bed temperature directly influence the structural and functional quality of the scaffolds [7].

Proper calibration of these parameters determines not only design fidelity but also the feasibility of their application in clinical or cellular research scenarios. Although multiple international studies address this topic, protocol standardization in local institutions remains limited [8].

This challenge is particularly relevant in the Colombian context. Although the Latin American regenerative medicine market reached a value of over 1.5 billion USD in 2024, with projected annual growth of 10% over the next decade, national investment in science, technology, and innovation still does not exceed 2% of GDP [9].

This reality significantly limits the implementation of emerging technologies such as 3D bioprinting, restricting the development of advanced biomedical solutions at the local level. Additionally, musculoskeletal diseases such as osteoporosis and associated conditions such as hip fractures show an increasing incidence in the country, which heightens the urgency of developing more effective and less invasive therapies [10,11].

To this biomedical need is added an environmental concern: the massive use of conventional petroleum-derived polymers in medical applications poses long-term ecological risks. In contrast, materials such as PLA and PCL, derived from renewable sources and capable of degrading without generating toxicity, represent a sustainable alternative. Their implementation in TE not only contributes to tissue regeneration but also aligns with environmental sustainability and circular economy principles [12].

2. METHOD

The development of the scaffold bank included three main stages: geometry design, 3D printing, and structural characterization. Three types of commercial polymers were used: polylactic acid (PLA), polycaprolactone (PCL), and a flexible filament (FLEX), selected for their mechanical properties, biodegradability, and compatibility with the fused deposition modeling (FDM) printing technique.

Scaffold Design: Two geometric configurations were designed: cubic and cylindrical, each with four types of pore patterns —square, triangular, rectangular, and diagonal (45°). The designs were created using CAD software (Autodesk Inventor®) and exported in STL format for further processing in the slicing software Cura®. The objective was to generate three-dimensional structures with controlled pores serving as physical supports for future cell culture tests (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The figure presents the project phases, from material selection and 3D printer calibration to scaffold design, fabrication, and characterization. Each stage was key to ensuring the structural and functional quality of the pieces. This process enabled the consolidation of an experimental bank with applications in tissue engineering.

3D Printing: Scaffold fabrication was carried out using a REGEMAT 3D R4L printer, specialized in biofabrication. Printing parameters for each polymer (extrusion temperature, print speed, layer height, and infill) were calibrated to obtain stable structures with good interlayer adhesion.

Morphological Characterization: To verify geometric fidelity and porosity, inverted and stereoscopic optical microscopy were used. These evaluations enabled analysis of structural integrity, confirmation of pore dimensional accuracy, and detection of potential defects introduced during printing.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Printer Calibration and Printing Parameters

Proper calibration of the REGEMAT 3D R4L printer was a determining factor in the successful fabrication of three-dimensional scaffolds. This process enabled the establishment of specific printing parameters for each polymer, optimizing structural quality, interlayer adhesion, and morphological precision of the pores. The importance of this stage lies in its direct impact on structure reproducibility and potential applicability in real TE contexts [13].

Printing parameters such as extrusion temperature, printing speed, layer height, and bed temperature were adjusted according to each material's rheological characteristics. Previous studies have shown that small variations in these values can lead to significant defects in the final scaffold structure, such as pore collapse or delamination [14].

3.2 Material Performance

The three polymers used (PLA, PCL, and FLEX) exhibited distinct behaviors during the 3D printing process. PLA demonstrated an optimal response to the established printing conditions, producing scaffolds with high

geometric fidelity, good interlayer cohesion, and well-defined pores. Its structural rigidity makes it an ideal material for applications requiring mechanical support, such as bone regeneration [15].

FLEX, despite being more complex to process due to its elasticity, enabled the fabrication of stable scaffolds with good pore definition. Its main advantage lies in its deformability, which could be useful for applications requiring higher flexibility, such as in cartilage or skin tissues [16].

Conversely, PCL presented greater technical challenges. Although it printed relatively stably at an extrusion temperature of 80 °C and a bed temperature of 40 °C, slight deformations in pore shape and variations in layer thickness were observed. This aligns with studies reporting that PCL, due to its low viscosity and reduced melting point, tends to exhibit dimensional instability if ventilation and print speed are not properly controlled [17].

3.3 Structural Evaluation of Scaffolds

Morphological validation of the scaffolds using inverted optical and stereoscopic microscopy allowed the analysis of characteristics such as porosity, layer uniformity, and pore geometry. This characterization was essential to verify the correspondence between the computer-aided design (CAD) model and the final printed structure [18].

PLA scaffolds showed the greatest uniformity and definition, with well-distributed pores and homogeneous layers. In contrast, FLEX scaffolds displayed small material overflows on internal walls, while PCL scaffolds tended to deform at corners and complex geometries, such as triangular pores. The pore geometry— grid-shaped, diagonal, or triangular pattern —also notably influenced scaffold dimensional stability, consistent with previous findings [19]. The results from stereoscopic evaluation are summarized in Tables 1–6, which present visual analyses of printed structures for each combination of material and geometric design. These observations helped identify specific behavioral patterns and guide print adjustments to improve final scaffold quality.

3.4 Biomedical Relevance and Functional Potential

Although certain deformations and irregularities were identified in some scaffolds, these results can be considered functionally valid. It has been demonstrated that microgeometric variations in scaffolds can mimic the natural heterogeneity of tissues, facilitating phenomena such as cell migration, angiogenesis, or topography-induced differentiation [20].

Additionally, the diversity of configurations designed in this scaffold bank allows the exploration of new experimental hypotheses. For example, polymer degradation rates could be compared as a function of geometric design, mechanical stress under physiological conditions could be evaluated, or nutrient diffusion efficiency could be measured across different pore patterns.

3.5 Institutional Impact and Academic Projection

The creation of this scaffold bank represents a strategic advancement for UCEVA in the field of biofabrication. Beyond generating functional physical models, the project strengthens student training in interdisciplinary areas and positions the institution as an emerging actor in the development of sustainable biomedical technologies.

This bank will not only serve as a basis for future research involving cell cultures but will also facilitate advanced teaching practices, experimental prototyping, and computational model validation.

3.6 Limitations and Future Perspectives

Among the main limitations of the study is the absence of advanced characterization techniques. The structural evaluation was optical, making it impossible to determine internal three-dimensional interconnectivity or the mechanical properties of the scaffolds. These aspects could be addressed in future studies through tools such as:

- Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)
- Mechanical testing (compression/tension)
- Thermal analysis (TGA, DSC)
- In vitro biocompatibility and cytotoxicity testing

Furthermore, it is recommended to study polymer blends such as PLA/hydroxyapatite or PCL/PEGDA, which have been shown to improve bioactivity, cellular support, and degradation resistance under physiological conditions [20].

Finally, incorporating computational models for simulating mechanical stresses and fluid transport in scaffolds would allow optimization of designs before experimental phases with cells or animal models.

3.7 Future Applications in Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine

The development and characterization of the 3D-printed scaffold bank not only represent an advancement in fabrication and design but also establish the foundation for its application in various areas of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine. These scaffolds could play a central role as temporary structures that support cell growth, differentiation, and organization within biomimetic environments:

- **Bone Regeneration:** Due to its high rigidity and good morphological definition, PLA emerges as an ideal candidate for bone regeneration applications, particularly in non-critical defects or in maxillofacial and orthopedic surgeries. When integrated with bioceramics such as hydroxyapatite or tricalcium phosphate, osteoconductive and osteoinductive scaffolds can be developed [21]. Moreover, by customizing pore geometry, it is possible to control vascularization rates and the degree of bone mineralization, which is key for the functional regeneration of hard tissues.
- **Soft Tissue Regeneration:** FLEX, owing to its elasticity, could be employed in the engineering of soft tissues such as skin, adipose tissue, or cartilage. Its ability to deform without fracturing makes it ideal for scaffolds that require biomechanical behavior similar to native tissue, for instance, in facial reconstruction or ligament regeneration [22]. Furthermore, incorporating biomolecules such as collagen, fibrin, or growth factors can promote cell migration, enhance adhesion, and stimulate connective tissue regeneration.
- **3D Models for Preclinical Testing:** One of the most immediate applications of these scaffolds lies in their use as three-dimensional models for in vitro assays, replacing traditional 2D systems that limit cellular physiology. These structures can be used to assess cytotoxicity, proliferation, cell migration, or drug responses, generating environments more representative of the human body [23]. In this sense, the scaffolds would serve as versatile platforms for testing in areas such as oncology, immunology, virology, or regenerative pharmacology.
- **Controlled Drug Delivery Systems:** Since the polymers used are biocompatible and biodegradable, these scaffolds can also function as controlled-release systems for therapeutic agents such as antibiotics, anti-inflammatory drugs, or even encapsulated stem cells. By manipulating porosity and layer thickness, it is possible to control release kinetics [24]. This opens the door to applications in localized treatments of bone infections, chronic wound regeneration, or combined therapies (drug + cell).

- **Stem Cell Therapies:** The three-dimensional architecture and bioinert nature of the materials used make them suitable for seeding with mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), allowing their use in advanced regenerative therapies. In combination with biochemical signals and mechanical stimulation, the scaffolds could induce cell differentiation toward specific lineages such as osteoblasts, chondrocytes, or myocytes [25].
- **Personalized Implants and Precision Medicine:** With the integration of medical imaging technologies (such as computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging), these scaffolds could be adapted to specific human body shapes, creating personalized implants. This customization is key in precision regenerative medicine, where implant design responds to the patient's individual morphology and the particular characteristics of the defect to be treated [26].

Table 1. Stereomicroscopy of cubic PCL scaffolds

		TAMAÑO DE ANDAMIOS (8x8x8)	
TAMAÑO DE PORO (mm)	TIPO DE PORO	IMAGEN COMPLETA	IMAGEN CON MEDICIÓN
1.0 x lado	Triangular		
1.0 x 1.0	Cuadrado		
1.0 x 2.0	Rectángulo		
1.5 x lado	Diagonal de 45°		

Table 2. Stereomicroscopy of cylindrical PCL scaffolds

		TAMAÑO DE ANDAMIOS (4x8)	
TAMAÑO DE PORO (mm)	TIPO DE PORO	IMAGEN COMPLETA	IMAGEN CON MEDICIÓN
1.0 x lado	Triangular		
1.0 x 1.0	Cuadrado		
1.0 x 2.0	Rectángulo		
5 x lado	Diagonal de 45°		

Table 3. Stereomicroscopy of cubic FLEX scaffolds

TAMAÑO DE PORO (mm)	TIPO DE PORO	TAMAÑO DE ANDAMIOS (8x8x8)	
		IMAGEN COMPLETA	IMAGEN CON MEDICIÓN
1.0 x lado	Triangular		
1.0 x 1.0	Cuadrado		
1.0 x 2.0	Rectángulo		
1.5 x lado	Diagonal de 45°		

Table 4. Stereomicroscopy of cylindrical FLEX scaffolds

TAMAÑO DE PORO (mm)	TIPO DE PORO	TAMAÑO DE ANDAMIOS (4x8)	
		IMAGEN COMPLETA	IMAGEN CON MEDICIÓN
1.0 x lado	Triangular		
1.0 x 1.0	Cuadrado		
1.0 x 2.0	Rectángulo		
1.5 x lado	Diagonal de 45°		

Table 5. Stereomicroscopy of cubic PLA scaffolds

TAMAÑO DE PORO (mm)	TIPO DE PORO	TAMAÑO DE ANDAMIOS (8x8x8)	
		IMAGEN COMPLETA	IMAGEN CON MEDICIÓN
1.0 x lado	Triangular		
1.0 x 1.0	Cuadrado		
1.0 x 2.0	Rectángulo		
1.5 x lado	Diagonal de 45°		

Table 6. Stereomicroscopy of cylindrical PLA scaffolds

TAMAÑO DE PORO (mm)	TIPO DE PORO	TAMAÑO DE ANDAMIOS (4x8)	
		IMAGEN COMPLETA	IMAGEN CON MEDICIÓN
1.0 x lado	Triangular		
1.0 x 1.0	Cuadrado		
1.0 x 2.0	Rectángulo		
1.5 x lado	Diagonal de 45°		

4. CONCLUSIONS

The construction of a three-dimensional scaffold bank made of PLA, PCL, and FLEX using fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D printing technology made it possible to establish a reproducible technical protocol for the fabrication of functional structures aimed at tissue engineering applications. The proper calibration of the REGEMAT 3D R4L bioprinter was a determining factor in ensuring design fidelity, scaffold structural quality, and pore dimensional stability.

During the experimental process, PLA proved to be the most stable material, with excellent geometric precision and good interlayer adhesion. FLEX, in turn, enabled the fabrication of elastic structures with adequate preservation of porous form, making it potentially useful for soft tissue applications. In contrast, PCL presented greater difficulty in maintaining the desired shape, highlighting the need for further optimization of printing parameters for this polymer.

The morphological analysis performed using optical microscopy was crucial to validate the printed structures, identify defects, and understand the behavior of each material under fabrication conditions. Although this technique allowed for a general evaluation of scaffold porosity and shape, a limitation was identified in its inability to analyze details such as nanostructure or internal interconnectivity, which could be addressed in future phases using more advanced techniques such as SEM, TGA, or DSC.

Despite some irregularities observed in certain designs, the results obtained are positive. The microimperfections present in the scaffolds may actually represent a benefit by more realistically simulating the structural complexity of biological tissues, potentially favoring cell interaction in future experimental tests.

This scaffold bank represents an important advancement for the Unidad Central del Valle del Cauca (UCEVA), not only for the technological development achieved but also for its projection as an experimental and educational tool. The generated models will serve as a foundation for interdisciplinary research in bioprinting, materials science, tissue regeneration, and biomedical design. Likewise, this work establishes a starting point for new research lines that include biomaterial combinations, structural modifications, and in vitro biological testing.

Taken together, this work strengthens institutional capacities in biofabrication and contributes to consolidating UCEVA—a higher education institution located in Tuluá, Valle del Cauca (Colombia)— as a regional reference in the development of technologies applied to regenerative medicine.

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